

Effectiveness of Individualized Education Plans: A Case Study of Parental Engagement in IEP Conference

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Abstract:- Families should actively participate in making educational decisions for their kids, and they can have a big impact on whether or not students with intellectual and developmental disabilities are included in the classroom. However, a lot of research has shown that parents do not believe that schools work well with them. A thorough analysis of the available empirical data from Google Scholar, ERIC and Research gate for original research studies published up to May 2022 was used to conduct the study, "Individualized Education Plans' Effectiveness: A Case Study of Parental Involvement in IEP Conference." A total of 178 parents from 7 studies—excluding overlapping study populations—made up the final sample. The study was guided by Vygotsky's (1978) theory of Zonal of Proximal Development (ZPD). According to parents' responses, institutionalised practices and certain school structures may frequently keep parents out of decision-making processes. Parents suggested involving parents in pre-meeting planning and organisation as well as regular communication between parents and educators outside of team meetings. When teachers prepared IEPs before the meeting, parents felt very discouraged and uneasy. The author's documentation of feelings of dissatisfaction, frustration, intimidation, and disenfranchisement stoked parents' thirst for knowledge and information. It was found that reports of unpleasant experiences were influenced by the efficiency of the services provided to students with special educational needs and the way that disciplinary issues were handled. Additionally, parents expressed concerns about the need for better transitional services and a desire for their children to have more inclusive opportunities. The findings have implications for parent-professional collaboration during personnel planning and decision-making for students with disabilities.

Keywords:- Individualized Education Plans, Parental Involvement, Conference

I. BACKGROUND

The Individualized Education Plan (IEP) is one of the most important and prevalent educational strategies used in education that includes students with SEN in the majority of schools around the world (Elder et al., 2018; Timothy & Agbenyega, 2018). The IEP is a specific type of written document created to validate the conclusions reached after

discussions among members of a multidisciplinary group about educational needs and service programs needed by children with SEN (Tran et al., 2018; Walther-Thomas et al., 2000). Children with SEN can gain access to the special education system, planned interventions, and support through the implementation of an IEP (Kauffman et al., 2018). Additionally, according to Groh (2021), the IEP can act as the foundation for delivering a free and suitable public education. When compared to the IEP, it can act as the foundation for delivering free and appropriate public education and comprehensively ensuring the effectiveness of an educational program in terms of design, implementation, monitoring, and compliance with the law (Rotter, 2014).

The communication between parents and school staff during the IEP conference is a complex relationship (Turnbull & Turnbull, 2001). Both parents and school staff have preconceived notions about communication going into the conference. Although their perceptions of this meeting may vary, the IEP conference creates the framework for fostering collaborative relationships between parents and school professionals (Ulrich & Bauer, 2003). Parents' opinions of the IEP conference frequently diverge from those of school staff members, even when there is no obvious conflict. This dichotomy includes upsetting and perplexing experiences, divergent opinions about the child's needs, a hostile environment, and a lack of an equal voice. When cultural factors are present, these perceptions are made worse (Turnbull & Turnbull, 2001).

The Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) is further proof of the IEP's significance in the special education system. According to IDEA, the IEP will be used to determine the programs and services that children with SEN need (Siegel, 2020). The existence of this IDEA legislation ensures the protection of all IEP implementation procedures. Accordingly, the act may specify the method or process for implementing this IEP service for kids with disabilities from birth to age 21. Additionally, IDEA can guarantee SEN children's right to receive FAPE in the setting with the "least restrictive" requirements. Additionally, teachers and parents have a significant impact on how children with SEN develop (Matheis et al., 2017; Subotnik et al., 2011). Teachers can be thought of as the key to success in IEP implementation, according to Fu et al. (2018). This is due to the fact that special education teachers should implement an IEP in the daily lives of children with

SEN, especially during school hours, and plan an IEP based on needs. The quality of the created IEP is significantly influenced by the teacher's perspective on the IEP implementation process, according to Fu et al. (2018).

The implementation of the IEP is crucial for every child with SEN, so it is important to identify any difficulties early on so that efforts can be made to overcome them. In order to implement the IEP for all SEN students in the school, teachers must overcome a number of implementation challenges. The inability to prepare an IEP, not knowing how to do so, and a lack of a variety of materials for IEP implementation are some of these difficulties (Akcin, 2022). With this context, this systematic literature review (SLR) is carried out with the intention of examining articles related to the difficulties in implementing IEPs for SEN kids. The analysis was done to determine the most typical competency issues that teachers run into when implementing IEPs.

A review of studies on the effectiveness of IEPs revealed that several studies from the first decade of the twenty-first century noted challenges with IEP use in schools. Studies by Andreasson et al. (2013) and Giota and Emanuelsson (2011), for instance, have demonstrated that the IEP has turned into a fairly standard practice in educational settings. However, a quarter of SEN students in schools do not have an IEP in place, according to both studies. The difficulty of implementing the IEP in China, according to Kritzer (2011), is due to a special education system that varies between schools, cities, and states, respectively.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The requirements of IDEA 2004 require that parents participate actively in the IEP meeting. Observational studies show that, despite the provisions, parental engagement, satisfaction, and participation in the IEP conference are less than ideal (Garriott, Wandry, & Snyder, 2000; Goldstein, Strickland, Turnbull, & Curry, 1980; Poland, Thurlow, Ysseldyke, & Mirkin, 1982; Rock, 2000). A further claim made by Katsiyannis and Ward in 1992 was that "many parents have little or no involvement in children's special education service" (p. 54). According to Spann, Koehler, and Soenksen (2003), "despite its need and importance, many parents have little or no involvement in special education" (p. 228), which was evidence in favour of their claim. Experiences that parents have prior to, during, and following the IEP conference may have an impact on their willingness to participate and collaborate with school staff. Congress believed that parents' roles in the special education process needed to be strengthened despite the original legislation's requirements for parental participation (Miles-Bonart, 2002; Rock, 2000; Silverstein, Springer, & Russo, 1992; Smith, 2001). P.L. 94-142 was thus replaced in 1990 by the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA). Among other changes to the law, the IDEA of 1990's section 612 mandated that disabled children should be educated alongside their peers who are not disabled "to

the maximum extent appropriate" and increased parental involvement in their children's education.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ibeanusi (2020) conducted research on how Hispanic parents and special education teachers perceived the involvement of individualized education plans. The key factors influencing parents' decisions to get involved are (a) their beliefs, (b) their sense of self-efficacy, and (c) the invitation to get involved. A suburban public school district chose 12 Hispanic parents of ELL students with disabilities from 4 schools across elementary, middle, and high schools for open-ended interviews, along with 6 special education teachers. Coding and thematic analysis of the interviewees' responses were part of the data analysis process. The results showed that Hispanic parents' limited participation in IEP meetings was due to their cultural background, lack of understanding of the special education system, and school invitations for involvement. Other themes included difficulty speaking English, rigid work schedules, disrespect, and stigma.

Senay and Kelesoglu (2019) carried out a study to assess the opinions of parents and teachers on parent participation in individualized education programs. The purpose of this study is to assess parents' and teachers' perspectives on parental involvement in IEPs. In this study, the qualitative method was employed. A descriptive survey model, one of the qualitative research techniques, was used to deeply examine the perspectives of parents and special education teachers and to force them to explain it in their own words. In order to learn more specifically about the opinions of special education teachers and parents of children with special needs regarding the creation and implementation of IEPs, the purposive sampling method was used in this study. 25 parents and 22 teachers took part in the study. Content analysis was used to examine the data. It was discovered that the majority of parents are unaware of IEPs. Additionally, it was discovered that parents are not invited by the school or institution to participate in the IEP process. Regarding the opinions of the teachers, it was discovered that they sometimes struggle to involve the parents in the IEP process. It was observed that teachers lack the necessary knowledge to include parents in IEPs.

Esquivel, Ryan, and Bonner (2008) looked at how parents perceived both the good and bad aspects of attending IEP meetings. Nine parent members of the special education advisory committee for the school district participated in this qualitative study. The parents responded to a survey asking them to describe the meetings they felt were the most positive (and negative) experiences they had in school meetings about their child. Parents' comments suggested that well-run meetings with fewer attendees and those where participants had distinct responsibilities all exhibited positive meeting traits. Parents reported that interactions with educators in the past and present had an impact on their experiences in school meetings. Professional relationships had an impact on team meetings as well. Parents wanted to know that their contributions and ideas were valued and

accepted, as well as those of the other team members. Parents praised the team's efforts to problem-solve and come up with original solutions. Parents believed that the nature of the information discussed at the IEP meeting affected the parents' emotional state. Overall, parents suggested involving parents in pre-meeting organization and planning and preferred regular communication between parents and educators outside of team meetings.

Lo (2008) used observations and interviews to investigate how Chinese parents felt about their kids' IEP meetings. Over a two-year period, Lo attended every IEP meeting for five kids with various disabilities. She took notes during the meetings about the way parents were welcomed, the number of people present, the questions parents asked, the frequency with which parents responded to professionals' questions, the number of comments parents started, and the meeting's goal. The IEP meetings were immediately followed by parent interviews. Lo conducted these in the language of the parents. Findings indicated that parents' attempts to participate in IEP meetings were hampered, if not rendered impossible, by the obstacles they faced. The language barrier made it difficult for all parents to communicate and comprehend what was going on during the meetings. When translators were offered, they lacked special education training and lacked familiarity with key terms, making accurate translation impossible. Parents believed that other members of the team did not value their suggestions and opinions. As a result, parents' inquiries were frequently ignored and decisions were made without their input. Additionally, since meetings were scheduled at the convenience of the school and not the parent, parents reported feeling disrespected when professionals showed up late or left early for meetings and when they openly criticized them. Author recommendations for enhancing the efficacy of IEP meetings included having professionals review terminology with translators prior to meetings, paying attention to parents' concerns to prevent misunderstandings, and working with neighbourhood organizations to create training for parents.

Three case studies with parents of Hawaiian ancestry were conducted by Sheehy (2006). Three families' experiences with educational decision-making, as well as the programs, placements, supports, and services their children received, were documented through informal interviews, phone calls, and observations. Each parent discussed challenges they overcame in their respective situations. Obstacles included lack of experience, ignorance of special education laws and the IEP decision-making process, resistance from educational professionals who were unwilling to seek parental input, and intimidation of parents who were not familiar with the IEP process. The Hawaiian parents who participated in the study defined involvement broadly, believing that it encompassed their attendance at school, informal conversations between parents and teachers, learning about special education, and advocating for their children. Therefore, these parents' involvement went beyond just having a say in the IEP meeting's decisions. When educators prepared IEPs prior to the meeting, parents felt very discouraged and uneasy. The

author documented feelings of dissatisfaction, frustration, intimidation, and disenfranchisement, which fueled parents' thirst for more knowledge and information.

Fish (2006) looked into the perspectives of seven parents who belonged to a particular family support group for parents of autistic children in north Texas. Semi-structured interviews were conducted and audio-recorded. Parents' opinions about the IEP meeting and any improvements they would suggest were sought out through interview questions. The following five free-form questions were posed: "Explain the caliber of services your child has received as a result of the IEP meetings with your child," "How are IEP team members treating and viewing you?" "What modifications to your child's IEP meetings would you like to see? The questions "What can parents do to improve IEP meetings?" and "What can school districts do to improve IEP meetings?" (Fish, p. 59). The majority of parents said their initial IEP experiences had been bad. The effectiveness of services provided to students with autism and the response to disciplinary issues were found to be contributing factors to the report of unpleasant experiences. Additionally mentioned were worries about the need for better transitional services and a desire for their kids to have more inclusive opportunities. Parents claimed that the school was to blame for their children's behavioural and academic issues. Additionally, the school rejected requests for particular services because they were unnecessary or too expensive. However, the study found that parents who brought an advocate to IEP meetings received better treatment from school staff. Parents reported an improvement in their relationship with the school as educators' knowledge of the child's disability and parents' knowledge of appropriate IEP procedures and processes increased. Parents suggested that a more democratic process could be used to make the IEP meeting better by allowing parents to feel like equal contributors, making decisions with their input, and appreciating and paying attention to their opinions.

A study on the individualized education plan: parental satisfaction and involvement was carried out by Habing (2004). Parents of children with special needs were surveyed for the current study. An organisation that supports families with children with disabilities mailed out 1,000 questionnaires, and only 348 of the parents returned the survey. It was discovered from the parents' written responses that 114 (33%) of the children they reported on were girls and 234 (67%) of the children they reported on were boys. The findings show that while many parents were happy with the IEP process, some parents expressed a number of serious concerns about their IEP experiences. About half of the parents who responded said they were very happy with how their child's IEP meeting turned out. The communication and partnership with the school were the most frequently cited benefits of the IEP process/meeting.

A. Objectives

- How do parents perceive the IEP meeting in their capacity as partners in their children's educational planning and as advocates for their needs?
- How do these experiences impact their involvement in the educational plan and program for their child?

B. Theoretical Framework

Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) (1978) by Vygotsky, which served as the study's guiding principle. The theory offers the IEP implementation framework for successful Special Educational Needs (SEN) learner instruction. According to this theory, learning occurs through the ZPD, where the word "zone" refers to the area where a learner needs the assistance of a teacher to complete a task that they are unable to complete on their own. The learner with SEN will be moved from his or her current level of performance to case, the learner with SEN will be moved from his or her present level of performance.

Rowland (2006) asserts that teaching is most successful when assistance is provided at the precise ZPD points where the student needs it and when there is distinction between what the student has learned and their level of performance during the learning process. The teacher should identify the needs of the learner with SEN as specified in the IEP in order to set goals for effective teaching in light of the aforementioned information and the context of this study. Thus, according to Vygotsky's theory of ZPD, the learner must be able to identify the gap in which they cannot perform independently, and the IEP must be used to provide support through accommodations, modifications, and effective instructional strategies. As a result, educators should assess the needs of students with SEN and provide effective instruction through IEP.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted using the SLR methodology. An SLR seeks to identify all empirical data that satisfies predetermined article selection criteria and responds to a particular research question or hypothesis (Moher et al., 2009). This is because information analysis is made possible by the SLR's requirement that explicit and systematic methods be used when seeking out and evaluating evidence. In order to select articles that were relevant to the stated research question, the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) flowchart was used in this study (Moher et al., 2010, 2015; Page et al., 2021). According to the PRISMA flowchart, the four stages of article selection were identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion of articles in the SLR study (Page et al., 2021).

A. Article Search Strategy

The article search for the SLR was conducted using three reputable databases: Google Scholar, the Educational Resources Information Center (ERIC) and Research Gate. The search term or keyword used is the most crucial component of the article search process, according to Joklitschke et al. (2018). In this study, two sets of keywords were used. IEP-related terms like "Individualized Education Plan (IEP)", "IEP process," and "IEP implementation" made up the first set of keywords. The second set's focus was on parental involvement, with the terms "parents' perceptions" and "participation in IEP meetings" used as keywords. During the article search process, both sets of keywords were combined using a Boolean search (AND, OR).

B. Article Selection Criteria

In order to establish criteria for article selection in survey research, which involves comparing a variety of literature sources, a clear and effective process is required, according to Xiao and Watson (2019). As a result, this study established a set of standards to aid in the literature search process. Only articles published within the last five years—from 2000 to 2022—were accepted in terms of the year of publication criteria. Regarding the language of the articles, only English-language articles from the two well-known databases were chosen and included in this study. Third, only journal articles were used in this study as the criterion for selecting the type of reference material. Books, conference papers, and proceedings, were not included as sources in this investigation.

C. Article Selection Process

The SLR's article selection procedure was conducted in January-June 2023. Figure 1 shows the modified PRISMA flowchart that Tawfik et al. (2019) assert represents the article selection process.

Fig 1 Flow Chart of Article Selection Process

This study's article selection process had four main stages, as shown in Figure 1. 82 articles were located at the identification stage using the two databases. Before the articles were added to the eligibility stage for a more in-depth and detailed screening, the articles were screened using the acceptance criteria in the following step. Before an article was included in the SLR study, it had to meet three additional criteria at the eligibility stage. These included articles without full text (n = 45), study titles that didn't make sense given the context of the study (n = 26), and articles in the form of reviews (n = 13) that did not meet the requirements for study acceptance. Only 12 of the 32 journal articles we downloaded were found to be suitable for use after review and analysis. This indicates that all 12 articles were successfully selected and included in the SLR after meeting all selection criteria.

V. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The seven journal articles that were obtained from the three databases—Google Scholar, ERIC, and Research Gate—were used in the data collection process. Table 2 lists the 7 articles as well as the publication year, nation, and study's goal. All of the chosen articles complied with the predetermined acceptance and rejection standards. For each article, data were gathered by abstracting the title, author(s), year, purpose of the study, and A table created with Microsoft Excel 2019 software shows how parents perceive the IEP meeting in their role as partners and how these experiences affect their involvement in the educational plan and program for their child. According to Kumar (2011), another goal of an SLR study is to create a conceptual framework based on the results of earlier research. This is so that the conceptual framework that was created can be used as a reference and added to the study's future literature section.

Table 2 List of Reviewed Research Articles

Author and Year of Publication	Study title	Country	Journal	Key Findings
Sheehey, P. H. (2006)	Parent involvement in educational decision-making: A Hawaiian perspective	Hawaiian	<i>Rural Special Education Quarterly</i> , 25(4), 3-15.	The parents' participation went beyond just having a say in the decisions made at the IEP meeting. Parents felt very discouraged and uncomfortable when teachers prepared IEPs in advance of the meeting. Parents' thirst for knowledge and information was stoked by the author's documentation of feelings of dissatisfaction, frustration, intimidation, and disenfranchisement.
Fish, W. W. (2006)	Perceptions of parents of students with autism towards the IEP meeting: A case study of one family support group chapter	Texas	<i>Education, Chula Vista</i> , 127(1), 56-68.	The majority of parents reported having negative initial IEP experiences. It was discovered that the effectiveness of the services given to autistic students and the way in which disciplinary problems were handled were contributing factors in the report of unpleasant experiences. Concerns about the need for better transitional services and a desire for their children to have more inclusive opportunities were also mentioned. Parents blamed the school for the behavioral and academic problems of their kids. The school also turned down requests for specific services because they were overpriced or unnecessary.
Lo, L. (2008)	Chinese families' level of participation and experiences in IEP meetings	China	<i>Preventing School Failures</i> , 53(1), 21-27	The challenges parents encountered made it difficult, if not impossible, for them to participate in IEP meetings. All of the parents found it challenging to communicate and follow the meetings' proceedings due to the language barrier. When translators were available, they were untrained in special education and unfamiliar with basic terms, which made accurate translation impossible. Parents felt that the other team members did not value their ideas and viewpoints. As a result, questions from parents were frequently disregarded and choices were made without their input.
Esquivel, S. L., Ryan, C. S., & Bonner, M. (2008).	Involved parents' perceptions of their experiences in school-based team meetings.	Chicago	<i>Journal of Educational and Psychological Consultation</i> , 18(3), 234-258.	Parents claimed that their experiences in school meetings were influenced by their interactions with teachers in the past and present. Team meetings were affected by professional relationships as well. Parents wanted to know that their contributions and ideas, as well as those of the other team members, were valued and accepted. Parents advocated for regular communication between parents and educators outside of team meetings and suggested involving parents in pre-meeting planning and organization.
Senay.S.J.; & Kelesoglu, A. (2019)	Evaluating Parent Participation in Individualized Education Programs by Opinions of Parents and Teachers.	Turkey	<i>Journal of Education and Training Studies</i> 7(2) 76-83	The institution or school does not invite parents to take part in the IEP process. It was found that the teachers occasionally find it difficult to include the parents in the IEP process. Teachers were found to be

				lacking the skills needed to include parents in IEPs.
Ibeanusi, P. (2020).	Perceptions of Individualized Education Plan Involvement from Hispanic Parents and Special Education Teachers.	Haspania	Thesis dissertation	Hispanic parents' low attendance at IEP meetings was a result of their cultural background, lack of knowledge of the special education system, and school invitations for involvement.
Habing, M. (2004)	Individualized Education Plan: Parental Satisfaction and Involvement	Chicago	Thesis dissertation	Although most parents expressed satisfaction with the IEP process, some parents voiced serious concerns about their IEP experiences. The majority of parents who responded said they were pleased with how their child's IEP meeting went. This percentage was around 50%.

VI. DISCUSSION

The researcher noticed that parents were not invited to IEP meetings, and even when they were, specialist teachers and head teachers gave similar responses. Parents with low levels of education found it difficult to ask questions, speak up, or interact with other parents during IEP meetings. Some parents received only rudimentary education or never attended school. Parents complained that the administration of the school had not emphasised the value of IEPs and that it was the job of the teachers to educate the children. These results are consistent with Fish's (2006) observation that the majority of parents reported having negative initial IEP experiences. It was discovered that the effectiveness of the services given to autistic students and the way in which disciplinary problems were handled were contributing factors in the report of unpleasant experiences. Additionally, as educators' understanding of the child's disability and parents' understanding of appropriate IEP procedures and processes increased, parents reported that their interactions with the school had improved.

Parents also asserted that their interactions with teachers in the past and present had an impact on how they felt about school meetings. Professional relationships had an impact on team meetings as well. Parents wanted to know that their ideas and contributions were valued and accepted, as well as those of the other team members. Parents proposed involving parents in pre-meeting planning and organisation and argued for consistent communication between parents and educators outside of team meetings Esquivel, Ryan, and Bonner (2008). These results are consistent with those of Shelley (2006) who discovered that parental involvement extended beyond just having a voice in the IEP meeting decisions. When teachers prepared IEPs before the meeting, parents felt very discouraged and uneasy. The author's documentation of feelings of dissatisfaction, frustration, intimidation, and disenfranchisement stoked parents' thirst for knowledge and information.

According to the study, parents are not invited to participate in the IEP process by the organisation or school. It was discovered that the parents' participation in the IEP process can be challenging for the teachers on occasion. Senay and Kelesoglu (2019) found that teachers lacked the abilities necessary to involve parents in IEPs. The outcomes are consistent with Fish 2016's findings, which indicated that the majority of parents reported having a negative first IEP experience. It was found that reports of unpleasant experiences were influenced by the efficiency of the services provided to students with special educational needs and the way that disciplinary issues were handled. Additionally, parents expressed concerns about the need for better transitional services and a desire for their children to have more inclusive opportunities. Parents attributed their children's behavioral and academic issues to the school. Additionally, the school declined requests for particular services because they were either unnecessary or too expensive.

Parents found it difficult, if not impossible, to participate in IEP meetings as a result of the difficulties they faced. Due to the language barrier, it was difficult for all of the parents to communicate and understand what was going on during the meetings. When translators were available, they lacked special education training and lacked a working knowledge of fundamental terms, making accurate translation impossible. Parents believed that their opinions and ideas were not valued by the other team members. Because of this, parents' queries were frequently ignored and decisions were made without their input. Lo (2008). The results are consistent with those of Ibeanusi (2020), who discovered that Hispanic parents' low attendance at IEP meetings was a result of their cultural background, lack of knowledge of the special education system, and school invitations for involvement.

Even though the majority of parents said they were happy with the IEP process, some of them expressed grave concerns. Most of the parents who responded expressed satisfaction with the way their child's IEP meeting went. This proportion was roughly 50%. The most frequently

mentioned advantages of the IEP process/meeting were partnership with the school and communication Habing (2004). Fish (2006) noted that the majority of parents reported having negative initial IEP experiences, which findings are at odds with. It was found that factors contributing to the reporting of unpleasant experiences included the effectiveness of the services provided to autistic students and the way in which disciplinary issues were handled. Parents also reported that their interactions with the school had improved as educators' understanding of the child's disability and parents' understanding of appropriate IEP procedures and processes increased.

VII. IMPLICATIONS

Diversity in disability type and severity, parent involvement, cultural issues, and teaching methods would broaden our knowledge base and aid in improving the calibre of educational programming provided to all students with disabilities. The results of this study demonstrate the need for additional research in the following areas: Identification of the factors that support and impede elementary students' participation in IEP meetings, and facilitation of younger children's participation. The IDEA has been renewed and is now in line with No Child Left Behind for all students enrolled in public schools. Allowing children/students to take the lead is perhaps the best way to ensure that no child is left behind. This is consistent with Vygotsky's theory, according to which learning takes place through the ZPD, where the word "zone" refers to the area where a student needs the help of a teacher to complete a task that they are unable to complete on their own. The learner with SEN will be moved from his or her present level of performance to case.

Teachers need to be aware that the IDEA's parent participation requirements have existed since the law's inception in 1975 (IDEA, 2004). The importance of parents' active involvement in their children's education is reiterated in the 2004 reauthorization. This also applies to IEP meeting decision-making. School administrators must be aware of the repercussions of not including parents in the IEP process. While some parents may require translators, others may require more latitude in the scheduling of meetings. Additionally, if at all possible, all necessary written materials for the IEP meeting should be given to the parents in advance. Parents should not be expected to make decisions if information is shared with them for the first time during the IEP meeting without having had enough time to read the documents. This includes giving parents the opportunity to ask any questions they may have and having the reports explained to them in a language they can understand. Parents' meaningful participation in the IEP is not encouraged by making them make decisions about the content of a document they have not had time to read in its entirety.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FURTHER DIRECTION

Based on the study's findings, the researcher came to the conclusion that special education teachers' abilities to create and implement IEPs were not up to par. The special education teachers are expected to evaluate each child's needs and create an IEP for that specific child in accordance with their training. It is obvious that a child with special education needs will perform poorly in both the academic and adaptive skill areas if he or she does not receive individualized instruction to meet his or her specific needs. There is also a ton of research available on the creation of IEPs. Very little research has been done in the African context, according to the evidence base for this systematic review, which may signal to stakeholders the need for more research on IEP as support programs for children with special education needs. When it came to the investigation of various parental perspectives, there was also an imbalance in the literature we reviewed because the majority of studies used them as a stand-in.

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